

THE ESSENCE OF USING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING STUDENTS TO CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract: The article describes in detail the essence of the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching students to think critically.

Key word: Modernization, educational technology, renewal, thinking, pedagogy, critical, pedagogical technology, creative, intellectual.

Today, in order to renew and modernize our country, to develop it on an innovative basis, to fulfill the multifaceted and complex tasks that we have set before ourselves, we are modern, creative and critical thinkers, and take responsibility in any situation. We are entrusting important tasks in state and society management to capable, enthusiastic, high intellectual potential, patriotic young personnel[1].

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev emphasizes that our country's worthy place among the developed countries and finding solutions to certain problems in society depends on the education of the young generation. For example, if we pay attention to the realization of our children's abilities from childhood and mobilize all our opportunities for their development, more Berunis, Ibn Sinas, and Ulugbeks will grow up in our country. I don't believe it[2]. In his speeches, the leader of our country expresses high confidence in the youth of our country.

One of the most important issues is to further increase scientific potential in higher education institutions, to expand the scope of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel training. It is necessary to increase the prestige of higher educational institutions, increase the number of non-state educational institutions, attract highly qualified personnel and strengthen competition. Because the more highly educated and highly qualified specialists there are in our society, the faster and more effective the development will be.

Development of critical thinking in students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy requires great skill, ability and experience from the pedagogue.

The most important thing for professors-teachers is to give thorough knowledge to students and educate them as physically and spiritually mature people. While researching the problem of using pedagogical technologies in the development of students' critical thinking, first of all, we should have enough information about the concepts of pedagogical technology and critical thinking. Since pedagogical technologies are a social necessity, they were first used in the 30s of the 20th century in the USA as "educational technology" and represented the use of audiovisual equipment in the educational process. In this case, the term "educational technology" is not only applied to teaching with the help of technical means, but also laid the foundation for a new direction in world pedagogy - pedagogical technology. The founders of

pedagogical technologies are B. Blum, D. Kratvol, N. Gronlund, J. Carroll, J. Blok, L. Anderson and others.

In the 50s of the 20th century, the use of technical tools in the educational process was recognized as a factor determining the direction of "educational technology", the main focus was on expanding the audience of learners, further improving the capabilities of technical tools, focuses on issues such as expanding their information capacity, quality organization of information transmission service, individualization of education.

In the beginning of the 60s, the organization of the educational process based on educational programming began to be seen as a place that reveals the essence of the concept of "educational technology". Programmatic education assumes that certain knowledge is given to students in a consistent, integrated manner, not in separate parts.

In the 1970s and 1980s, "educational technology" was recognized as a branch of theoretical knowledge of pedagogy, which represented the educational process that guarantees the achievement of pre-planned and clearly defined goals, as well as information technologies in education.

With the passage of time, as a result of the expansion of the level of use of pedagogical technologies, the content changed accordingly. In 1979, the American Association of Pedagogical Technologies and Communications ended the debate about the meaning of pedagogical technologies and announced their official definition: "Pedagogical technology is the acquisition of people's ideas, knowledge, It is a complex integrative process that includes means of planning, provisioning, evaluation and management activities [3]. Currently, all pedagogic-psychological scientists recognize the following definition of UNESCO as the most perfect definition of pedagogical technology: It is the use of the integrated approach method in the design and implementation of the learning process" [4].

It can be seen that the basis of educational technology is the idea of full implementation of this process in order to increase the effectiveness of education and to guarantee that students will achieve the planned learning results in the given conditions. The essence of such an approach is to systematize the educational process - to maximize its formation with the help of clearly formalized and divided into specific elements.

Based on the above rules, the subject of pedagogical technologies consists of designing the educational system, from proving the conceptual foundations, choosing and structuring educational materials, choosing an educational model to their implementation, and evaluating their optimality and effectiveness. [5].

Modern pedagogical technologies based on didactic improvement and redevelopment of educational material. These technologies are based on principles such as the didactic system of studied knowledge having a deep content, approaching knowledge from a systematic point of view, and teaching students the most appropriate ways to acquire knowledge.

Modern pedagogical technologies based on effective management and organization of the educational process. These technologies include differentiated, individualized programmed educational technologies, collective method of education, group, computerized educational technologies.

Modern pedagogical technologies adapted to nature. These include modern pedagogical technologies based on the full use of the natural possibilities of organizing the educational process of students and other natural possibilities.

Modern developmental educational technologies. These include technologies for developing the positive qualities of students' personalities, knowledge in certain fields, and creative abilities.

In addition to these, there are directions of private (educational subjects), alternative and author modern pedagogical technologies.

Scientific studies, monographs and manuals (V.P. Bespalko, V.V. Guzeev, M.V. Klarin, V.M. Monakhov, V.Yu. Pityukov, G.K. Selevko, etc.), articles (T.S. Nazarova, LYa. Dyachenko, etc.)) analysis shows that in the structure of pedagogical technologies, the following directions are distinguished, the main of which are empirical, cognitive, heuristic, creative, inversion, integrative, adaptive, inclusive pedagogical technologies. The main features of this direction are as follows:

Empirical - gaining knowledge through the senses. In this technology, the main attention is focused on imparting knowledge based on the natural development possibilities of sense organs and further improving them.

Cognitive - a technology for expanding the range of knowledge about the surrounding world. It forms differentiated thinking, critical thinking, and develops knowledge needs.

It is necessary to teach by asking heuristic - guiding questions. It is an educational method that serves to develop ingenuity, activity, and attention.

It has a creative-research character and rapidly develops goal-oriented creative thinking and critical thinking in students.

Inversion is a feature of studying information from different angles, replacing it, and develops a critical thinking system.

Integrative - determination of the only correct conclusion based on the inextricable interdependence of the infinite number of small parts that make up the information, their integrity, unity.

Adaptive - achieving the expected result on the basis of facilitating and adapting information and the process of its use for learning and teaching.

Inclusive - organization of the educational process on the basis of equality in the interaction between the teacher and the students.

Currently, in addition to the above, there are other areas of modern pedagogical technology that are being tested by experts.

It is known that if a person does not have a critical attitude to what he knows and learns, there will be no independence of thinking in the activity of knowledge.

The criticality of thinking is characterized by a person's ability to strictly evaluate his own and other people's opinions, fully prove and comprehensively check all the rules and conclusions put forward. A person with critical thinking never considers his thoughts to be absolutely true, flawless and complete. He always tries to test them in practice, and if his ideas do not correspond to reality, he looks for methods and evidence to answer them. Critical thinking is first of all an orderly, strict and responsible mind that does not accept everything as believable. Those who have a non-critical way of thinking accept any information they come across as their own.

Therefore, at the stage of development of the society today, the issue of educating independent, free and critical thinking young people is the most urgent task before us.

For this reason, it is necessary to activate the cognitive activity of students, to improve their independent and critical thinking abilities in the organization of the educational process at all

stages of the continuous education system. After all, it is important for students to know how to sort the information of the world and to learn to critically, creatively and effectively evaluate what is important and what is not important. First of all, in order to know how to manage and sort information well, students should develop practical knowledge, critical thinking skills and abilities. This gives them the opportunity to effectively sort and choose information and ideas based on critical thinking, it leads to correcting the information and ideas that have been selected, and they can be turned into practical forms of action. In other words, it is necessary to turn them into habits of critical thinking. However, critical thinking is not formed by itself. They should develop experience and skills in obtaining useful information and opinions.

The process of critical analysis must continue regularly, the result of critical thinking is the development of critical thinking. In order for this to happen, teachers should use modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching involuntarily.

So, what is critical thinking? Regarding its definition, there are different opinions and assessments. According to some researchers, "critical thinking", "analytical thinking", "logical thinking", "creative thinking" and others - and we can agree with this, remembering the etymology of this word. "Criticism" (Greek *kritique* - "evaluation, analysis, discussion"); Consequently, "critical" means "evaluation, analysis". Critical thinking (alternatively dogmatic) can be understood as creative, analytical and constructive thinking. From the pedagogical point of view, we consider it as an active and interactive learning process. Critical thinking is interactive, creative, reflective thinking. Critical thinking means understanding and realizing one's own, objective, logical, perception of other points of view.

In addition, there are several definitions of the term "Critical thinking". Including J. Still, K. Meredis and Ch. Temple's manual "Chtenie i pismo dlya razvitiya kriticheskogo myshleniya", ("Reading and writing for the development of critical thinking") as a system of universal principles of teaching, in which the extensive use of interactive teaching methods is used for the effective development of critical thinking. it is stated that it allows.

The famous American philosopher and pedagogue D. Dewey defines the essence of critical thinking as follows: "Only a person's critical thinking in relation to the conditions and results of experience can direct personal desires and interests."

Diana Halpem writes in her book "Psikhologiya kriticheskogo myshleniya" ("The Psychology of Critical Thinking"): "Critical thinking is a form of cognitive skills and strategies that increase the likelihood of achieving a desired result, which is based on restraint, logic and purpose. is distinguished by orientation".

Anderson and his co-authors say, "Effective continuous learning for new situations is a problem for us to understand information and ideas. Pupils can achieve the highest results only when they actively absorb information and ideas.

According to Polinskar and Brown, "the learning process will be more successful only when various strategies for the development of thinking activity are used. In this case, the strategies ensure that the educational process is more conscious.

According to Resnik, "students will develop knowledge and creative thinking only if they can apply their knowledge in solving specific problems".

According to Ross, "learning that builds on students' prior knowledge and experiences is reinforced. All this gives students the opportunity to connect new information with what they already know.

According to Banks, "Critical thinking and reading will only work if teachers properly understand the diversity of ideas and experiences." If the spirit of "one answer" prevails, then critical thinking will be encouraged."

According to Agapov, "Critical thinking is aimed at developing students' skills in working with text, mastering all forms of oral and written speech, exchanging ideas with peers on a specific text (communication skills, group work skills) is a pedagogical technology". Critical thinking is changing the atmosphere in the classroom, giving it a touch of enthusiasm, and making the lessons a joy for the pedagogue and students. Such a technology is based on ideas such as the plurality of points of view of thinking and interpreting the text, reflexivity of the cognitive process, modern understanding of culture. The idea of personal worth and its development, self-realization and creation of favorable conditions for realization are the most important.

John Barrell defines the following characteristics of critical thinking people[6]:

Critical thinkers:

- can solve problems;
- show a certain tenacity in solving problems;
- controlling oneself, impulsivity;
- openness to other ideas;
- able to solve problems by cooperating with other people;
- can listen to the interlocutor;
- empathic;
- has resistance to uncertainty;
- can consider problems from different points of view;
- able to establish many connections between events;
- they tolerate a point of view other than their own;
- can consider several options for solving the problem;
- often ask questions: "What if?";
- can make logical conclusions;
- thinking about feelings, thoughts - evaluating them;
- able to make predictions, justify them and set active goals;
- can apply his skills and knowledge in different situations;
- curious and often asks "good questions";
- actively perceives information.

In conclusion, "A person has critical thoughts, gets acquainted with one or another idea, and takes into account the important consequences of their implementation. At the same time, a person initially perceives these ideas with a certain level of distrust and compares them with opposing points of view. He uses a system of additional considerations to justify them and develops his own point of view based on them. Critical thinking is a complex process of combining ideas and possibilities with creativity, as well as reconstructing a concept. It is also a process that takes place simultaneously at several levels of active and interactive cognition. A critical thinker will not be influenced by various tricks and unhealthy ideas, because he will have his own strong personal views.

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